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**RUSSIAN EMPIRE WORKS ON IMPROVING THE SURKHAN OASIS
IRRIGATION SYSTEM****СОЗДАНИЕ РОССИЙСКОЙ ИМПЕРИЕЙ ИРРИГАЦИОННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ
В СУРХАНДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ**©*Kabulov E.**Ph.D., Termez State University**Termez, Uzbekistan, eshbolta@mail.ru*©*Кабулов Э.**канд. ист. наук**Термезский государственный университет,**г. Термез, Узбекистан, eshbolta@mail.ru*

Abstract. The given article highlights the works of the Russian Empire done on improving the irrigation system of Surkhan oasis. There given factual information supported by archive materials and scientific literature.

Аннотация. Автор рассматривает историю развития системы водоснабжения и орошения Российской империей в Сурхандарьинской области. Представлены архивные сведения по ряду мероприятий и дается краткий аналитический обзор.

Keywords: Surkhandarya, Salavat, Pattakesar, Gilambab, Tallashqan, Maydaaryk, aryk, Navshahar, channel.

Ключевые слова: Сырдарья, Салават, Патта-Гиссар, Талашган, Майдаарык, канал.

The main purpose of Russian Empire in agrarian politics in Turkistan was to solve the cotton problem, and for solving this problem, some measures would be put into practice on irrigation system. In the first years, administrators of Empire did some works on irrigation system to satisfy requirements for food products and to improve water supply of the cities and the villages, where Russian inhabitants and soldiers live. And in this situation, we can say the acts in Termez city for example. The Tsarist government did some necessary measures and they kept Termez city tightly because of Surkhan oasis borders with Afghanistan, and the Englishmen put some demands to Bukhara emirate by this country. And the most important problem was the water supply. In 1889, some measures were produced for the lands, which is 10 thousand tithe around Termez city to be watered by Kizilsuv [1, p. 88].

Only in 1897, crops of local population were reduced, and 20 families had to migrate to other places. The main problem was water shortage [9,59]. Shymensky who was the captain of Russian Empire wrote about it: “Although our demands are not fair, local population must shorten their crop areas and satisfy our requirements on watering. Our newcomers don’t know to economize water” [9, p. 59].

In December 1897 restoration works were begun on Salavat channel to improve provision of irrigation. And in the same year B. N. Kastalsky bought 474,5 tanab–135 hectares land, for 52.500 tanga from local people [3, p. 248].

Russian Empire officials buying lands from oasis area lasted continually. They determined that in spite of not having irrigation constructions, they can assimilate and sow agricultural crops in the land of 1000 square verst with water of Surkhandarya [1, p. 88]. And additional land was demanded for strengthening garrison and accommodating the military forces. In 1900 emir of

Bukhara drew up a statement and according to it the Kattakum desert in the north, Surkhan river in the northern–east, and triangle–formed land which total area was 10.514 desyatina borders with Amu–darya were donated to the Russian Empire providing that not withdrawal. And in exchange it Abdulahad who was emir of Bukhara asked to give him the title of “Russian general” or to reward with supreme symbol called “Andrey Pervozvanny”. Then he was awarded “Russian general” title [2, p. 1–2].

Termez city, which is the center of region and the lands around it were given to Russia for that title. Termez and Pattakesar destination, which obtained by Russia, firstly were military fortification. The total area was 11.600 desyatina land and 9935 desyatina land was property of Russia and the rest 1655 desyatina land that was the villages Pattakesar, Solihabad and Manguzar were private property of local population although the land was officially belong to Russia. So 683 desyatina land area belonged to Pattakesar, and the rest 982 desyatina land was the area of other villages.

The parts of Pattakesar, which was belonged to the Russians was 250 desyatina, and this land was ruled by Termez military garrison. The 682 desyatina land of 2462,5 which was donated by Emir of Bukhara was irrigating, and 1780,5 desyatina land was non–irrigating [8,52]. There were even problems of irrigating lands in watering. Because Salavat and Pattakesar canals, which provided these lands with water were not reliable irrigation system. Salavat channel was damaged at the sowing phase by Surkhan river, when its water rised. It took weeks to restore it. Besides that, aryks were sometimes full of mud and sand and this situation demanded the huge part of peasants to conduct to clean all waterlines. The Tsarists government gave a task to the engineering court with the purpose of improving irrigation system. In 1898, N.M. Gelman designed water construction project, which was cost 130 thousand roubles for watering 4750 desyatina ground around Termez city. Russian officials knew that 40–50 roubles would be demanded for each desyatina land, it would cover its expenses during three or four years, then it would bring more profit [13, 173; 1, 90].

Military engineering court spent 160–170 thousand roubles for maintaining irrigation system and constructing new ones. The lands, which donated by Emir of Bukhara was given to the private entrepreneurs as a rent for a year providing they pay 27.979 roubles. And besides that, people paid tax the amount of 1200–1500 roubles for a year for using water [7, 52].

The lands around Termez were given to entrepreneurs and the offices of Kingdom, as a rent by military engineering course and they put some clauses as following: irrigating lands were given for 5 years and non–irregating for 10 years [7, 52]. Lessors who took the lands for a rent are required to keep the irrigation ditches clean and fit.

At that time representatives of local authority began to build new irrigation buildings with the help of local people to solve watering problem. In 1906 deputy of emir of Bukhara signed a contract with local village elders to mine water to Sherabad. According to the contract, they agreed to mine water for the land of 1005 tanab on the direction of Djarkurgan. This agreement was signed among duty of political administration of Russia in Bukhara, Mirza Salimbek, the head of Sherabad and judge Khudja Abdulla [5, P.340]. It is noticeable that project of Zang canal which was began to construct in 1908, was drawn by Ishanbek, who showed the way of canal about 55–60 kilometers long, riding on the horse. The head of Sherabad supervised digging of canal himself. Digging work was implemented in two shifts and about 4 thousand people participated in it [6, 80].

Djarkurgan canal was widened to Zang village. Zang canal was divided into 12 small waterlines and they supplied nearby villages wiyh water. In September 1911, local population addressed to Emir of Bukhara with the aim of widening Zang canal. The head of Sherabad took constructions from Emir to implement of nation and in 1912 widening work of Zang canal put into practice. This canal was stretched until Navshahar with the help of workers of Gilambab, Tallashqan, Maydaaryk, and Robikhudjaby. Local people settled down to the new assimilated lands [4, 309].

The Tsarist Government considered this land not only as military area, but also the field of economical benefit. Russian irrigators and meliorators were invited to the oasis to solve watering

problem of all planting fields. Besides this in irrigation lands cotton and cereal were planted [12, p. 65]. To develop irrigation system at the end of 191, the Emir of Bukhara and Russian government signed a contract in the Eastern Bukhara. According to the contract 250 thousand roubles were devoted to put into practice planned works, and 69.000 roubles of this money were spent for pools and canals and watering the lands around Bukhara city in 1912 [10, 6].

In spring, 1912 special society called “Watering investigation party of Bukhara” was compiled by I. Bloomberg who was the specialist on road building. This party consisted of 14 people. The main purpose was as following: –building hydro–constructions by learning perfect the situation of rivers, lakes, pools and waterlines of Bukhara; –digging canals and waterlines; –finding places to build water–barn; –opening up new lands in short time with spending little money. In general Bukhara watering investigation party, led by Bloomberg spent 195674 roubles, 70 coins during 5 years [10, 6]. The money given by Russia directed to increase planting cotton and opening up new lands. Especially, because of lack money of government, this process was slowed down. The Tsarist government tried to draw private capital. This matter was discussed at the meeting of government among representatives of private capital managed by A.V. Krivosheyn on June 5, 1909 [11, 95–96]. Additional laws had to be created, during the process of considering statement at the meeting. And those law projects were following: “Law about irrigation in Turkistan by private capital” and “Agreement about creating big and small irrigation establishments”. Those law projects were prepared at the end of 1912 and proper permissions were taken in April, 1913. And at that time A.V. Krivosheyn achieved to take “the highest permission” on another matter too.

As a result, concession (agreement) or contract on creating irrigation fields was given to the winner in tender (to present project, which its indexes are the cheapest and the best). According to the new laws it was informed that watering lands which its term was not less 36 years and area was more than 5 thousand desyatina were to let in “Establishment of wide irrigation” [11, p. 95–96].

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